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Blended Learning and Continuous Assessment as Tools to Promote Active Learning in an Electronics Product Design Course

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INTRODUCTION

Multiply skilled professionals is what the modern working life is seeking for. Mastering the theoretical skills of one's own field is not enough, but several other skills, such as social, presentation, teamwork, problem-solving and time management skills are expected from the new engineers. In addition, the students should finish their studies in a reasonable time to master the time-related pressures for their studies from the government and from the financial point-of-view.

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In order to answer the above-mentioned challenges it is important that students are actively engaged in the learning process. This paper introduces a teaching experiment in which elements of blended learning and continuous assessment were used as tools to activate students in their learning process. The aim of using the blended learning and continuous assessment was also to offer students versatile and flexible learning opportunities. The framework of this experiment was a bachelor level university course of electronics product design at Tampere University of Technology (TUT) at the department of Electronics and Communications Engineering during autumn 2017. The course duration was 14 weeks and the extent was 4 credits (ECTS). Thirty-three students participated and passed the course. At the end of the course, student feedback was collected and the results of the feedback are summarized in this paper.

1 BLENDED LEARNING AND CONTINUOUS ASSESSMENT

Blended learning can be defined in several ways, but a simple form of definition defines it as a combination of face-to-face instruction with computer-mediated instruction [1]. This seems easy and natural way of learning as information and communication technology is such an integral part of new university students. It is however important to notice that at its best the blended learning integrates the strengths of the face-to-face and online learning environments and avoids their weaknesses [1]. A careful design is thus needed, so that the blended model is not just an add on to the existing dominant method, but the face-to-face interaction and the asynchronous online interaction are merged in a manner that the students are offered learning experiences not conceivable via either modes separately [2,3]. In this way, blended learning can facilitate a community of inquiry, in which all three elements: cognitive, social and teaching, are present and thus a meaningful learning can occur [3]. The advances of combining these two teaching methods include, among others, pedagogical richness, access to knowledge, social interaction, cost-effectiveness and flexibility [1]. It has also been indicated that the implementation of blended learning can result in higher degree of utility, motivation and satisfaction among the participants and thus a positive attitude towards learning can occur [4].

The possibilities to combine these two learning environments are limitless and several different forms and levels of blended learning exist. Blending can occur at activity level, course level, program level, or institutional level [1]. Course-level blending, the most common way to blend, consists of a combination of distinct face-to-face and online activities used as part of a course [1]. These activities can overlap in time or be sequenced chronologically [1]. The teaching experiment presented in this paper is considered a course-level blending as the course consists of different activities some of which occur in a classroom while others are realized in a Moodle learning environment.

1.1 Continuous Assessment

Assessment is often used for grading purposes and such an assessment is generally referred to as summative assessment. Formative assessment on the other hand usually involves feedback so students can improve their performance.

Continuous assessment often has both summative and formative function by grading students' achievements and by supporting their learning process [5]. In the teaching experiment described in this paper the continuous assessment has both these functions. Firstly, all the different assignments and the three electronic exams that were distributed along the course were compulsory requirements for completing the course. Thus, students needed to work continuously during the course. As some of the assignments and all the electronic exams were graded, they had the summative

function. Feedback, either individual or group level, was given from all the assignments and exams so they had the formative function of supporting the learning process as well. Overall, continuous assessment can have a positive effect on learning as it has been indicated that continuous assessment can make the students to adopt a more continuous learning style and motivate them to study [6]. The most traditional structure of many engineering courses with lectures, exercises and a final pen-and-paper exam that determines the course grade does not necessarily activate students' learning process evenly throughout the course nor does it offer students much flexibility of scheduling their studying.

2 COURSE IMPLEMENTATION

Electronics product design is a third-year bachelor level course and its main target is to provide students with basic knowledge on the different hierarchical levels, production processes and design perspectives of an electronic product. To complete the course students had to gather 19 points out of 38 points. Points were given from the two group works, one calculation exam and from the three electronic exams. Grade three required 27 points and grade five 35 points. The evaluation was performed on a scale of Excellent (5), Very good (4), Good (3), Very satisfactory (2), Satisfactory (1) and Fail (0).

As the amount of information in this course is quite high, the course was divided into five blocks. Each block reflects a major theme of the course and consists of several smaller topics. One block lasts 2 - 5 weeks depending on the extent of the theme. The amount and form of learning events and assignment included in each block were designed so that they support learning of the theme topics, offer versatile learning experiences as well as flexibility to students and distribute workload evenly throughout the course. The detailed course content is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Electronics Product Design Implementation in Autumn 2017

Block	Weeks	Main topics	Learning events	Learning assignments
1	1-2	Introduction to the course Wafer manufacturing Integrated circuit manufacturing	2 lecture events 1 group work presentation event	Group work Electronic exam
2	3-5	Electronic package, through-hole and surface mount technology Wire bonding and flip chip Soldering (wave and reflow)	3 lecture events 1 wiki assignment wrap- up event	Wiki assignment Electronic exam
3	6-7	Basics of printed circuit boards Flexible printed circuit boards	2 lecture events	Group work Laboratory work
4	8-9	Basics of thermal management and heat transfer mechanisms Thermal design	2 lecture events 1 calculation exercise event 1 calculation exam	-
5	10-14	Basics of reliability and reliability testing Basics of testing and testing strategy Quality and Six sigma Environmental aspects Wrap-up	5 lecture events 1 group work wrap-up event 1 calculation exercise event	Group work Forum discussion Electronic exam Voluntary individual assignment

2.1 Learning events

The twenty face-to-face learning events consisted of lectures, calculation exercises, one calculation exam and different wrap-ups of the learning assignments.

The lecture events of the course were designed so that they introduce students to each topic. The learning assignments then complemented these lectures and enabled students to deepen their knowledge on the topic. All lectures were also designed to be interactive and activating meaning that they included teacher's questions, Kahoot-quizzes, group and pair discussions and small exercises. The Kahoot-quizzes were used in the beginning of lectures to revise the core contents of the previous lecture and to have a fun and activating start to the lecture. Teacher's questions, discussions and small exercises were applied during the lectures to encourage students own thinking and to practise discussion and argumentation skills.

The purpose of the group presentation and wrap-up learning events was to offer students the possibility to present their work; how the group realized the assignment, what was the outcome of the assignment, did the group work go as planned and was the distribution of work even. In these events, students were also able to see how other groups realized the assignments. By presenting their assignments students learned presentation and communication skills, which are important future career skills. Other important career skills – calculation and problem-solving skills – were learned in the calculation exercises and in the calculation exam. In the exercises, students were able to work together, thus share their knowledge, and jointly come up with a solution. The calculation exam then consisted of two problems and students had two hours time to give answers. The maximum points of each problem was four.

All these different face-to-face learning events had an important social aspect in the blended course model. In the learning events students had the possibility to group, strengthen their belonging to the group, interact with themselves and with the teacher and share opinions and understanding. It has been indicated that such face-to-face events can support team development, commitment and accountability to team members [7]. In addition, among learners these face-to-face events give a sense of community and thus students do not feel isolated and have a higher risk of dropouts. Fully online courses would lack such sense of community. [8]

2.2 Learning assignments

The aim of the nine compulsory learning assignments was to enable students to continue their learning process after the introductory lectures and thus to deepen their knowledge on the topic.

For the group works students formed groups of four to five people. In the first group work the target was to study the basic process steps of making an integrated circuit. Each group had one topic and they prepared a 10-minute learning session from this topic. The topic of the second group work was applications of flexible printed circuit boards and in the third group work the students needed to do an operating condition and reliability testing specification for a coolant temperature sensor. In each group work, the students wrote a report and presented their outcomes. Each group realized their work as they wished meaning that some groups preferred to meet face-to-face while other group realized their group work mainly online. The group works were designed to promote collaborative learning and to increase students' teamwork, information retrieval, communication, interaction, design and documentation skills. Teacher wrote feedback for each group regarding their work. The first and the third group work were graded on a scale of 1 – 6 points and the second group work was scaled passed/failed.

With the laboratory work, which was done in pairs, the students gained hand-on experience with printed circuit board manufacturing process. The students made a double-sided printed circuit board and soldered the components. Each group were able to choose between making a decibel meter or a FM transmitter. The laboratory work included also preliminary and follow-up reporting and it was graded passed/failed.

The wiki assignment and the forum discussion were fully online assignments. These were also done in the same groups of four to five people. In the wiki assignment the students wrote a wiki about surface mount technology in the Moodle learning environment. Each group was responsible of a certain topic in the wiki. In the wrap-up learning event each group then presented their work and explained how their realized the assignment. This wiki assignment was graded passed/failed. For the forum discussion each member of the group were given a role: a thermal design engineer, an electrical design engineer, a production/test design engineer and a printed circuit board design engineer. The group then had to discuss and select one component out of predetermined components to be used in a smart phone. Each student had to write at least three messages in the Moodle by giving one's reasons for the component, making questions and arguing for other components. Group also had to write a short summary that was then gone through in the wrap-up learning event. This assignment was also graded passed/failed. Teacher wrote feedback for every group from both these assignments.

The electronic exams were individual and they were realized with the EXAM electronic exam system. The students had 50 minutes time to answer each exam and the exams were graded on a scale of 1 – 6 points. Teacher wrote feedback for each student.

3 STUDENT FEEDBACK

At the end of the course, a student feedback was gathered with an online feedback system. The questionnaire consisted of multiple choice questions and open questions. The total number of respondents during the academic year 2017 – 2018 was 30.

Table 2. shows the overall rating of the course and its implementation during academic years 2015 – 2018. In the 2015 – 2016 implementation, the only compulsory requirements of the course were the similar laboratory work as described in the chapter 2.2 and a final electronic exam. The lectures and exercises were arranged in a certain time and place, but they were optional. During the academic year 2016 – 2017, the course consisted of various activating lecture and exercise learning events. Students had to gather a certain amount of points by taking part in the learning events or by completing separate written exercises in order to pass to course. In addition, the same laboratory work and the calculation exam as described earlier were compulsory requirements in the course. The final electronic exam was optional, but it was possible to raise the course grade by taking it.

Table 2. Overall rating of the course and its implementation

Academic year	Number of respondents	Mean	Mode	Median	Standard deviation
2017 – 2018	30	4.27	4.0	4.0	0.63
2016 – 2017	21	4.05	4.0	4.0	0.58
2015 – 2016	35	4.21	4.0	4.0	0.63

As the Table 2. shows the mean of the overall rating during 2017 – 2018 was 4.27. This is slightly more than in the previous years as during 2016 – 2017 the mean was 4.05 and during 2015 – 2016 it was 4.21.

In Fig. 1 the overall rating of the course and its implementation is further compared during academic years 2015 – 2018. As the Fig 1. indicates, 90 % of students found the course during academic year 2017 – 2018 very good or excellent. This is also slightly more than in the previous implementations of the course. It seems that the course structure that was implemented during the academic year 2017 – 2018 was successful as the overall rating of the course increased.

Fig 1. Overall rating of the course and it implementation

Many students found that the working methods used in the course made the course versatile, deepened learning, made it more meaningful and developed group work skills. This is indicated in the following quotations regarding the question “How did the working methods used during the course affected your learning?”:

“Working methods were the best part of the course and helped, as it were by accident, with getting familiar with the topic, and they brought nice variation. I recommend also in future.”

“By thinking yourself or in a group issues stick in one's mind very well, which lowered the need to read for an exam. Revision before the EXAM was enough. The flexibility of the EXAMs was also convenient for me.”

“The working methods deepened learning and developed group work skills.”

“Learning was more meaningful compared to the traditional course structure.”

Many students also found the continuous assessment positive. It seems that the continuous assessment divided the workload evenly throughout the course, made learning easier and made at least some students to adopt a more continuous working style. The following quotations regarding the question “How did the calculation of the final grade based on the sum of learning exercises and the EXAM exams affect your learning?” indicate this:

“Very nice as a whole, splitting up the topics made learning easier.”

“One had to study evenly throughout the entire course”

“Throughout the course one made and kept in mind the course things. EXAM exams split the topics up to good entities. - > improved my learning.

“Positively as the workload was divided evenly throughout the course.”

“One stressed less for an exam. Studying one block at a time is easy.”

“One revised the learned topics right away so I believe they stick better in one’s mind.”

Few students felt that the workload was too heavy and that there were too many assignments. However, 91.67 % of students found that the course workload corresponded to the number of credits.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The teaching experiment presented in this paper has shown that blended learning and continuous assessment elements can help in activating students in their learning process. The results of the experiment indicate that such a course structure offers students versatile learning experiences, which can make students feel positively towards learning and thus make it more meaningful. Blended learning methods can furthermore make learning deeper and develop group work skills. Continuous assessment on the other hand can make students to adopt a more continuous working style. These results support other findings, which indicate that by blending the face-to-face and online learning environments students still get the important social aspect of learning, which is then supported by the online learning experiences offering students time to ponder, process and have online conversations independent of time and place [2, 7]. This can lead to a positive attitude towards learning and facilitate a higher learning experience [3, 4]. Continuous assessment can also affect positively on learning and thus students may learn in a more continuous manner [6].

Another important aspect of such a course structure is the flexibility it offers compared to the traditional face-to-face course structure. As part of the learning assignments in the course are independent of time and place students have more possibilities to complete the course, if they e.g. work along studies or have overlapping learning events. Finland’s Ministry of Education and Culture has recognized in their development plan that work along studies, inflexible teaching arrangements and problems with study skills and motivation are factors slowing down studies [9]. A course structure implementing blended learning elements can help students in their time management and thus make studies more efficient.

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